

PREVALENCE OF CESTODE INFECTIONS IN ALBINO MICE AND RATS EASTERN: A PUBLIC HEALTH THREAT

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ABSTRACT

Cestode infections are known to be common in man and rodents all over the world. Cestodes of rodents (*Hymenolepis spp*) are also known to infect man. The number of mice and rats used for experimental studies are on the increase. The prevalence of cestode infections in albino mice and rats in Michael Okpara University of agriculture, Umudike and University of Nigeria, Nsukka and their environs was investigated. Faeces were collected from 350 albino mice and rats each and screened for the presence of cestode eggs by flotation and McMaster techniques. Sixty six percent and fifty percent of the rats and mice respectively were found to pass cestode eggs in their faeces. Cestode infection was present in both study areas. The egg per gramme (EPG) ranged from 1 to 4,500 in rats and 1 to 2,000 in mice. Five mice were found to excrete pinworm eggs. Mite eggs were found to be very common and adult mites were also observed in a few cases. Given that cestodes (*Hymenolepis diminuta* and *H. nana*) of rats constitute a zoonosis, breeders and users of rats and mice should observe strict personal and environmental hygiene in order to minimize the chances of being infected and the spread of the infection. It was concluded that mice and rats may be routinely dewormed to improve productivity of the animals, their quality as research animals and to reduce the risk of human infection.

KEYWORDS: Albino mice and rats, zoonosis

INTRODUCTION

Infection of rodents with *Hymenolepis species* is very common (Soulsby, 1982). According to a review by Cross (1994) human cestodiasis occurs worldwide and prevalence and distribution are related to eating habits of population groups. Rats, mice and other rodents are important because of their role as experimental animals, pets, major vectors of human and domestic animal diseases worldwide (Anantaraman, 1966; Huq *et al.* 1985; Woerpel and Rosskorpf, 1991). They are also increasingly being bred as a source of income and their litter is used as manure. However, just as in livestock and poultry these animals also have helminth and arthropod parasites that usually infect them. Cestode parasites may hinder profitable productivity of animals and reduce their value as experimental animals and pose some zoonotic threat to their handlers (Lightowlers, 1996).

Unlike in livestock and poultry, control of diseases including parasitic diseases of rats, mice and other rodents is not very much emphasized. However, vaccine research for the control of cestode infections is on (Lightowlers, 1996); and *Hymenolepis nana* infections of human has been reported to be treated with praziquantel (The Veterinary Merck Manual, 1986).

It was hypothesized that the prevalence of cestode infections in rats and mice would be very high. There would therefore be a need to educate handlers of the animals on the zoonotic importance of the infections and the need to observe good sanitary practices and control of the infection in rat and mice population, thereby improving their value as experimental animals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Three hundred and fifty adult (6-32 weeks old) and young (3-5 weeks old) male and female rats and mice each were sampled from May to April to September in 2010. They were kept in Michael Okpara University of

Agriculture, Umudike (MOUAU), University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN) and their environs either for research, teaching and breeding for sale in various Departments, Research Units or individual homes.

The management system was virtually the same and resembled the deep litter system in the poultry. Briefly, feed was either poured directly on the floor of the cages, put in shallow plastic, ceramic or metal cups or bowls. In a few situations feed was pelleted into large rods as described by Ngongeh (2004) and either placed in troughs inbuilt in the cages or suspended on pieces of wires into the cages. Water was either served in water bottles or in open plastic, metal or ceramic cups.

Faecal collection

Faeces of rats and mice were obtained according to the method of Ngongeh (2008, 2011), where they are placed in large plastic cups and bowls and allowed to defaecate.

Faecal egg counts

Faecal egg counts were done by both the flotation and modified McMaster techniques. Initially the flotation was employed. Faeces was weighed, macerated in saturated sodium chloride solution and passed through a fine coffee strainer to trap the residue. The residue was discarded while the filtrate was put in test tubes and more salt solution added until a convex meniscus was formed. Cover slips were then placed over the tubes and removed after 3 minutes and viewed under the microscope. Eggs where present, were counted and divided by the weight of faeces to obtain the egg per gram of faeces (EPG). Where more than 100 eggs were detected, then the eggs on the slide and cover slip were recovered by rinsing with the saturated salt solution into a petri dish and together with the suspension in the test tube transferred into 50 ml graduated Teflon tubes. The volume of the salt was then adjusted and counted by the modified McMaster technique as described by Fakae (1993). Briefly the presence of cestode eggs in the faeces was checked and quantified where present by the Modified McMaster technique. Other egg types were also noted.

Statistical analysis

Results were analysed using standard statistical procedure, Student's t-test and difference with probability level, $P < 0.05$ was accepted as significant.

RESULTS

Cestode eggs were present in 66% (231) of the rats and 50% (175) mice from all the sources and in varying numbers (Table 1). The percentage prevalence is presented on Fig. The prevalence of cestode infections was quite high in both rats and mice. The incidence was however, significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in rats than in mice (Fig 1). There were a lot of variations in FEC with individual FEC ranging from 1 to 4,500 EPG in rats and 1 to 2,000 in mice. The incidence was higher in adult rats and mice than in their young counterparts given that 77.9% (180) adult and 22.1% (51) young rats were found to be infected while 80% (140) adults and 20% (35) young mice were infected. However, where infection was present in the young most animals were infected in such cages. There was no evidential sex discrepancy in the incidence of infection in rats given that 118 and 113 male and female rats respectively were infected. In mice 51% (89) and 49% (86) male and female mice were infected giving no meaningful sex difference as in the case of the rats.

Aspicularis (pinworm) eggs were recorded in mice. Mite eggs were quite common in both mice and rat faeces but prevalence was more so in mice populations than rats. Some rats and mice had alopecia suggesting mite infestation.

Table 1: The number of rats and mice infected with cestodes and percentage prevalence.

Animal species	Total number of animals sampled	Number of animals infected with cestodes	Percentage prevalence of cestode infections
Outbred albino rats	350	231	66
Outbred albino mice	350	175	50

DISCUSSION

The results showed that cestode infections are very common in intensively managed rats and mice in the areas investigated especially in the adults. The high prevalence may be due to the poor management system in which the animals, feed and faeces are usually in contact. The feed might therefore be contaminated with cestode eggs and infected intermediate hosts wherever the infection is present thereby ensuring the cycle of infection. The poor husbandry practice in which there is failure to regularly clear off the litter before provision of fresh feed is unhygienic and would favour the cycling and multiplication of the infection in the population.

Hymenolepis infections had been reported to be more common in populations that live under conditions of poverty and poor hygiene especially where fleas are present (The Veterinary Merck Manual, 1986). Basic hygiene practices such as washing of hands after handling rats, mice and other rodents have been strongly commended.

From enquiries made, no form of anthelmintic remedy is adopted to control the infections and no diagnosis of helminth infection is commonly done but for the author who conducted some diagnosis and treatments in outbred albino mice before use in experimental studies (Ngongeh, 2011). The only control method is therefore the clearing of litters which in some animal units (ratteries and miceries) was only done when convenient to the owners and when the litter has built up enough to be collected for manure in most cases. Regular cleaning of cages was however found to be common in some units especially when experimental studies were on. A low prevalence of *Hymenolepis spp* (19.5%) has been reported in *Rattus rattus* in Nsukka area where UNN is sited (Onyenwe *et al.*, 2009). This low prevalence may be due to the husbandry system whereby the feed may not be heavily contaminated with infective cestode eggs since they usually disperse their faeces over a large area compared to intensively managed albino rats and mice that are confined in cages with their repeated mixing of their faeces with feed as already described in their management system above.

Wild rats and most rodents usually have preferred locations for defaecation rather than soiling their feed or sleeping quarters with the faeces. The lower prevalence in the young rats and mice compared to their older counterparts could be due to the relatively short exposure time of the young to the infective material and their likely less voracious feeding habit compared to their older counterparts that have had longer contact with the faeces. The fact that most or all the young animals in some cages were infected once the infection was present is in line with the fact that younger animals are more susceptible to parasitic infections than the older ones (Ngongeh *et al.*, 2007; Ngongeh, 2011). Though there was no significant disparity in the prevalence of infection, the females had slightly higher prevalence than the males. This may be due to the fact that females are allowed to live longer for breeding purposes compared to males which are often used or sold out for use in experiments leaving only few for mating the females. Males seemed to be preferred too compared to females perhaps to

avoid the chances of pregnancies which may alter some parameters such as body weights. The presence of mite eggs in some rats and mice is significant since such arthropod vectors transmit diseases from animals to man (Khatoon *et al.*, 2004). Mites may also serve as the intermediate hosts of *Hymenolepis* as does fleas.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Though cestode infections are usually mildly pathogenic to their host especially in low worm burdens, its control in rats and mice would be necessary especially given that the infections constitute a zoonosis. Kharton *et al.* (2004) had reported that rodents spread parasite eggs in their faeces to the fields, grain stores and in food stuffs in houses. Anthelmintic treatments, proper sanitary practices such as proper disposal of rat and mice faeces and treatment of litter to be used for manure and regular emptying and cleaning of water containers for the provision of clean fresh water. Feed remnants should also be discarded before introduction of fresh feed. Proper hygiene observation such as the washing of their hands once animals are handled is strongly advised. These practices would break the transmission of infection, lead to production of quality research animals and save the handlers the risk of zoonosis. It was recommended anthelmintic drugs with high efficacy and more practical methods of their application be investigated and made known to breeders and users of rats and mice.

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